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Two-way Coupled Fluid-Structure Interaction Model for a Tidal Turbine

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Abstract

The present study is motivated from the fact that turbine blades experience a complete cycle of reversed stress during each revolution. Tidal turbine blades are usually designed as thin as possible to optimize the performance and minimize manufacturing cost. However, due to the stress, turbine blades are deformed, and it can cause adverse effects on power performance and structural integrity. Conventional design studies on tidal current turbines are conducted by Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) with a simple rigid blade assumption or Finite Element Analysis (FEA) with simplified hydrodynamic loads from low-fidelity methods. However, this simplification can cause errors in prediction of the device reliability and the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE). In the present study, a coupled Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) model to obtain accurate solution for loading and performance of a deforming rotor is developed, and the impact of FSI on hydrodynamic and structural parameters are investigated for a tidal turbine rotor.

Keywords: Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI); Tidal Turbine; Numerical Simulation; Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD); Finite Element Analysis (FEA)

1. Introduction

Tidal energy presents a promising avenue for harnessing renewable energy, yet tidal turbines confront substantial challenges arising from the harsh and unpredictable marine environment in which they operate. A critical hurdle in the design of tidal turbines lies in the ability to maintain their performance and durability under diverse loading conditions, a task influenced by the intricate interplay between water currents (fluid) and turbine structures. This interaction causes blade deflections during operation, and potentially induces oscillatory behaviors like flutter, which can compromise structural integrity and power efficiency. Accurately capturing this phenomenon necessitates the application of Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) analysis.

Over time, numerical simulations have emerged as a convenient and reliable research methodology, bolstered by consistent validation through model experiments conducted on tidal current turbines by researchers [1-4]. Among the numerical approaches, the Blade Element Momentum (BEM) method has been widely employed in studies aiming to characterize tidal current turbine performance. Concurrently, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has experienced substantial development, becoming an essential tool due to its ability to leverage computational resources effectively. Utilizing these numerical approaches, several FSI investigations on tidal and ocean current turbines have taken place.

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For instance, Young et al. [5] developed an FSI model by coupling BEM and Finite Element Analysis (FEA) solvers, enabling the simulation of transient hydroelastic responses in tidal turbines. However, the BEM approach's limitation lies in its two-dimensional force representation, neglecting spanwise flow and potentially leading to imprecise hydrodynamic characteristics. Liu et al. [6] explored structural performance using a CFD-FEA one-way FSI model, examining different blade materials and rotational speeds. Similarly, Ullah et al. [7] undertook fatigue-life and modal analyses, yet the one-way FSI model's assumption of negligible structural deformation limits its capability to study the effects of blade deformation on turbine performance. Addressing this limitation, Park et al. [8] introduced a CFD-FEA two-way coupled FSI model, investigating the impacts of blade deformation and yawed inflow on tidal turbine performance. This study revealed blade deflection towards downstream and a subsequent decrease in power output. Nonetheless, the study was constrained by the Moving Reference Frame (MRF) method's inability to account for transient blade deformation effects accurately. Further investigations by Badshah et al. [9] and Zhang et al. [10] evaluated hydrodynamic and structural aspects through CFD-FEA two-way coupled FSI models, comparing simulation results against CFD and analyzing factors influencing turbine performance. However, none of these previous studies jointly examined computational mesh and time step size dependencies while incorporating the overset mesh technique for rotor rotation, which demonstrates improved accuracy in capturing wake dynamics and unsteady effects [11].

In this study, we propose a novel two-way coupled FSI model for a 0.5m diameter lab-scale Reference Model 1 (RM1) tidal turbine [12]. This model synergistically couples the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) solver, Ansys Fluent, and the Finite Element Analysis (FEA) solver, Ansys Mechanical. The two-way coupled methodology involves solving fluid and structural equations independently while exchanging boundary conditions at the fluid-solid interface. Within each time step, FEA computes structure deformation in response to hydrodynamic forces. This deformation is then incorporated into the CFD mesh to compute subsequent hydrodynamic load changes for the ensuing time step. We comprehensively compare key hydrodynamic parameters such as performance coefficients, torque, and thrust obtained from both CFD standalone and FSI models. Additionally, we delve into structural parameters, including deformation, stress, and strain, which profoundly influence turbine longevity and performance. Through a rigorous comparison between CFD standalone and FSI models, we aim to discern the impact of fluid-structure interaction on these critical parameters.

2. Modeling Approach

2.1. CFD Model

The CFD model utilizes a tetrahedral mesh with overset multi-blocks for computational grid generation. The adoption of an overset mesh provides enhanced control over local mesh characteristics as the geometry moves within the domain. The medium grid configuration comprises approximately 29 million cells, while the fine and coarse grids consist of about 65 million and 15 million cells, respectively. The first cell's y^+ is set to 1.4 for the medium grid. To resolve the viscous sublayer of turbulent boundary layers, a total of 20 prism layers with a growth rate of 1.2 are generated on the rotor and nacelle walls. These prism layer parameters are established based on empirical correlations for turbulent flow boundary layer thickness over a flat plate.

A chamfer is incorporated along the spanwise direction of the blade, with a thickness equivalent to 1% of the chord length, to mitigate skewed mesh elements and enhance mesh quality near the blade's trailing edge. The Shear Stress Transport (SST) $k - \omega$ turbulence model [13] is employed for modeling turbulent flow in the CFD computations. The Pressure-Based Coupled Solver (PBCS) concurrently solves for pressure and momentum. A second-order upwind scheme is adopted for spatial terms, while first-order implicit methods are used for temporal terms across all governing equations, including the turbulence model and momentum equations. The gradient interpolation of diffusive fluxes, velocity derivatives, and higher-order discretization schemes is achieved through the utilization of a least squares cell-based method.

2.2. FEA Model

The FEA model focuses solely on the rotor geometry, with the assumption that the deformation of the nacelle is negligible. To streamline model complexity during this developmental phase, the rotor's solid structure is represented

using hexahedral mesh with quadratic element order. The rotor material model is assumed to be an aluminum 6061-T6. Inclusion of the effects of centrifugal forces is achieved by assigning an angular velocity corresponding to the turbine's rotation speed. The rotation at the turbine hub center is modeled by constraining the rotor through a remote displacement support.

2.3. FSI Model

FSI models are classified based on the coupling methods employed between CFD and FEA solvers. The choice of coupling method hinges on the degree of physical coupling between the domains. For scenarios where small deformations are encountered, a One-way FSI model suffices, involving the transfer of hydrodynamic loads from the CFD analysis to the FEA analysis. Conversely, situations involving substantial deformations necessitate a two-way coupled FSI model, where deformations are predicted and subsequently fed back between the FEA and CFD models.

In this study, an iteratively implicit two-way coupled FSI method is adopted. The CFD and FEA solvers independently solve their respective equations, iterating within each time step to obtain an implicit solution. The iterative process comprises three levels: the inner loop, converging fields within each solver; the coupling loop, updating calculated forces and displacements between the CFD and FEA solvers; and the transient loop, advancing in time. The schematic representation of this model is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the developed two-way FSI model.

3. FSI Simulation and Discussion

In this study, comprehensive investigations are conducted using both one-way and two-way coupled Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) models on the scaled RM1 tidal turbine equipped with solid aluminum alloy blades within an experimental channel [12]. Initial examination through the one-way FSI model involves pre-stressed modal analysis, revealing that the applied load frequency remains comfortably below the rotor's natural frequencies. In light of these results, a comparison is drawn between CFD simulations conducted in a previous study [14] and the outcomes of the present two-way coupled FSI simulation. The focus is on power and thrust coefficients, with observed changes within a 1% range across various tip speed ratios (TSR). This minimal alteration is attributed to the small deformation, as the solid rotor geometry in the current model restricted deflection to below 0.4 mm. Notably, at higher TSR values, more pronounced performance coefficient disparities between CFD and two-way coupled FSI simulations are noted, particularly in power coefficient variations.

Additionally, an in-depth analysis of hydrodynamic and structural parameters is carried out, encompassing performance coefficients, directional and rotational deformations, equivalent elastic strain, and equivalent stress. This assessment seeks to elucidate the influence of blockage, introduced by adjacent walls, on these parameters.

The development of the two-way coupled FSI model holds paramount significance in evaluating tidal turbine performance and characterizing structural loads. This model's ability to yield stress, strain, and deformation profiles throughout a rotation cycle, while predicting turbine performance changes arising from blade deflection, is a notable advancement. As an invaluable tool, this FSI model is poised to contribute substantially to predicting the performance and longevity of tidal turbines across diverse loading scenarios. Its capacity to accurately capture the intricate fluid-structure interaction lays the groundwork for optimizing turbine designs to achieve peak efficiency and durability.

The implications of this study's findings reverberate across the marine energy sector, providing a solid foundation for refining and advancing sustainable energy technologies. Engineers, designers, and researchers can leverage the insights from this study to enhance the design and optimization of tidal turbines, aligning with the US Department of Energy's goal of reducing marine renewable energy costs while bolstering performance. This model's applicability extends to future studies, where it will be extended to assess the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) for full-scale tidal turbines made from diverse materials, including aluminum and composites.

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References

- [1] Lee JH, Park S, Kim DH, Rhee SH, Kim M-C. Computational methods for performance analysis of horizontal axis tidal stream turbines. *Applied Energy*. 2012;98:512-23.
- [2] Masters I, Williams A, Croft T, Togneri M, Edmunds M, Zangiabadi E, et al. A Comparison of Numerical Modelling Techniques for Tidal Stream Turbine Analysis. *Energies*. 2015;8(8):7833-53.
- [3] Marsh P, Ranmuthugala D, Penesis I, Thomas G. The influence of turbulence model and two and three-dimensional domain selection on the simulated performance characteristics of vertical axis tidal turbines. *Renewable Energy*. 2017;105:106-16.
- [4] Doan MN, Alayeto IH, Kumazawa K, Obi S. Computational Fluid Dynamic Analysis of a Marine Hydrokinetic Crossflow Turbine in Low Reynolds Number Flow. *Volume 2: Computational Fluid Dynamics* 2019.
- [5] Young YL, Motley MR, Yeung RW. Three-Dimensional Numerical Modeling of the Transient Fluid-Structural Interaction Response of Tidal Turbines. *Journal of Offshore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering*. 2010;132(1).
- [6] Liu XF, Wang JB, Tian ML, Tang ZB. Efficiency and Performance Analysis of Tidal Current Energy Turbine Basing on the Unidirectional Fluid-Structure Interaction. *AMM* 2014;672-674:386-91.
- [7] Ullah H, Hussain M, Abbas N, Ahmad H, Amer M, Noman M. Numerical investigation of modal and fatigue performance of a horizontal axis tidal current turbine using fluid-structure interaction. *Journal of Ocean Engineering and Science*. 2019;4(4):328-37.
- [8] Park S, Park S, Rhee SH. Influence of blade deformation and yawed inflow on performance of a horizontal axis tidal stream turbine. *Renewable Energy*. 2016;92:321-32.

- [9] Badshah M, Badshah S, Kadir K. Fluid Structure Interaction Modelling of Tidal Turbine Performance and Structural Loads in a Velocity Shear Environment. *Energies*. 2018;11(7).
- [10] Zhang Y, Liu Z, Li C, Wang X, Zheng Y, Zhang Z, et al. Fluid–Structure Interaction Modeling of Structural Loads and Fatigue Life Analysis of Tidal Stream Turbine. *Mathematics*. 2022;10(19).
- [11] Lopez Mejia OD, Mejia OE, Escorcía KM, Suarez F, Laín S. Comparison of Sliding and Overset Mesh Techniques in the Simulation of a Vertical Axis Turbine for Hydrokinetic Applications. *Processes*. 2021;9(11).
- [12] Hill C, Neary VS, Gunawan B, Guala M, Sotiropoulos F. US department of energy reference model program RM2: experimental results. Sandia National Lab.(SNL-NM), Albuquerque, NM (United States); Univ. of Minnesota, Minneapolis, MN (United States). St. Anthony Falls Laboratory (UMN-SAFL); 2014 Aug 1.
- [13] Menter FR. Two-equation eddy-viscosity turbulence models for engineering applications. *AIAA journal*. 1994 Aug;32(8):1598-605.
- [1] Kim D, Gunawan B. Coupled Fluid Structure Interaction Simulation on a Horizontal Tidal Current Turbine. UMERC+METS 2022 Conference; 2022 Sep. 13-14; Portland, OR.